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The use of artificial intelligence technologies in the innovation activities of industrial enterprises.

Annotation. Artificial intelligence plays a key role in the innovation activities of industrial enterprises, representing an important area of technological development within the framework of the 4th Industrial Revolution. During the half-century process of development of AI technologies, machine learning and the growth of computing capabilities, modern multilayer neural networks have already become effective tools for modeling complex control and management functions in technological industries. Against the background of current trends, the Industry 4.0 paradigm integrates artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, big data analysis and other technologies to create intelligent production systems. Smart factory, smart mine and other projects are being actively implemented around the world, with artificial intelligence tools playing a key role in them.

Keywords:artificial intelligence; industry; industrial enterprise,digital transformation;technology; economics; Industry 4.0; Industry 3.0; neural networks.

Аннотация. Искусственный интеллект играет ключевую роль в инновационной деятельности промышленных предприятий, представляя собой важное направление технологического развития в рамках 4-й промышленной революции. За полувековой период развития технологий искусственного интеллекта, машинного обучения и роста вычислительных возможностей современные многослойные нейронные сети уже стали эффективными инструментами для моделирования сложных функций контроля и управления в технологических отраслях. На фоне современных тенденций парадигма "Индустрия 4.0" интегрирует искусственный интеллект,

Интернет вещей, анализ больших данных и другие технологии для создания интеллектуальных производственных систем. "Умная фабрика", "умная шахта" и другие проекты активно внедряются по всему миру, и инструменты искусственного интеллекта играют в них ключевую роль.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект; промышленность; цифровая трансформация; технологии; экономика; Индустрия 4.0; Индустрия 3.0; нейронные сети.

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) is one of the main technological directions for the development of the digital transformation of industry, which means that they play an important role in the innovative activity of the enterprise. The very concept and technology AI has come a long way since the middle of the 20th century, when fundamental research and experiments began, which were supposed to determine which human tasks AI could perform better, faster and with a lower percentage of errors. In evolutionary development AI's main task was formulated quite quickly: unlike classical automation and robotization, AI must solve precisely "human tasks", although creative, but well-algorithmized and logical. Therefore, the first practical attempts by A. Newell and G. Simon in the late 50s of the last century consisted in the development of software that imitated human thinking (for example, in proving mathematical theorems or in dialogues with an operator).

Modern AI tools used In industrial digitalization projects combine both approaches in their creation and development: so expert systems have tens of thousands of complex dependencies in the program code, and effective AI tools in the field of "computer vision" or "digital twins" undergo long-term training on huge amounts of data. By the end of the 20th century, AI tools had received industry specialization and were already solving certain classes of problems in economics on a par with performing similar tasks by humans. This rapid development was facilitated by overcoming the most important limitation — the limitation on computing power. The development of machine learning by the 21st century has become much more complicated, has received a whole set of automation tools and has become an independent technological direction within the framework of the development of artificial intelligence. The effectiveness of machine learning has been continuously increasing over the past twenty-five years, and one of the significant milestones has been the development of self-learning principles.

The modern Industry 4.0 paradigm represents the next stage in the technological evolution of industry, combining artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT) and big data analysis (Big Data) to create fully automated and intelligent production systems. Examples of such systems are the implementation of "smart factory", "smart mine", "smart warehouse", etc. In the

Industry 4.0 paradigm, the availability of technologies such as the Internet of Things, computer vision, industrial Wi-Fi, data warehouses and non-relational databases allows processing huge amounts of data in real time, making AI learning and improvement mechanisms even more effective [4].¹The Industry 4.0 paradigm itself has made significant contributions innovations in the technological and innovative development of industrial enterprises. The most promising technologies should be highlighted:

- intelligent Internet of Things;
- AI-driven engineering;
- predictive systems based on.

These technologies have become an integral part of modern integrated solutions and have an impact on various aspects of competitive activity in industry. For example, "smart factories" have already been created in Germany, where production management systems developed, for example, by Siemens automatically regulate production processes in real time, based on data on demand and equipment condition. This significantly increases production efficiency and reduces costs. For example, Mercedes has built such a fully autonomous car factory, where production by robots is controlled by AI systems in real time, processing huge streams of data about all production lines, inventories, raw materials and logistics processes.

The study defines the current level of demand for AI tools and identifies significant trends of scientific and practical interest and potential directions for the formation of effective policies in the competitive development of industrial enterprises. The first and main conclusion from the study is that the use of AI tools in industrial production remains "piecemeal", experts associate the change in the situation with a whole set of complex factors:

- disadvantages of the digitalization methodology (from economic aspects will the project of implementing an AI solution pay for itself to the technical aspects of their operation and development);

- the need to significantly reduce the costs of AI implementation projects (including: eliminating the shortage of hardware and software, overcoming the isolation of the technological sector of the economy, returning IT specialists who left).

There is still a huge potential for industrial enterprises to use large language models (LLMs) like GPTChat, Google Bard, Microsoft Copilot, YandexGPT, etc. The Russian industry does not seem to understand the revolutionary changes in production and business processes that this class of solutions brings. Only about 16% of experts use such systems (and then informally or experimentally).

The task of integrating any AI tools into a common one also remains unresolved. The IT landscape of an industrial enterprise: the study showed literally a

single experience of integration with the most important enterprise systems (ERP, MES, CAM, external systems). In the vast majority of cases, AI tools literally "float in the air" because their use is truncated by a set of atomic tasks, and the data and results of their work are not sent to other information systems.

The results of the study showed the level of demand for AI tools in production processes in the Russian industry from the point of view of the Industry 3.0 paradigm. The second conclusion is made: the potential for the use and development of AI technologies within this paradigm remains significant. Almost all significant technologies (automation, robotics, expert systems) from the Industry 3.0 paradigm, developed since the end of the 20th century, can be enhanced by AI tools. However, for a significant part of the enterprises (more than half) that participated in the study, these steps are still far from being implemented.

The study presented the experience of using AI tools in the context of the Industry 4.0 paradigm: there is an increased interest in technology Artificial Intelligence of things. Nevertheless, the application of "Computer Vision with AI elements" technology faces certain difficulties. Almost 90% of experts report incomplete effectiveness of the solutions used in this area, which indicates the need for additional research and financial investments in this direction.

The accelerated development of the concept of AI-driven engineering in industrial enterprises is also noted. In conclusion, it should be noted that the study participants associate the further development of all AI tools with public investment in the industry. This means that the direction of AI in the innovative development of industrial enterprises needs significant investments of various types, and at the basic level and in current economic conditions — long-term government support.

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